

FRIES REARRANGEMENT OF ESTERS OF 2-METHYL-4-BENZOYLPHENOL

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Fries rearrangement of 2-methyl-4-benzoylphenyl acetate, propionate, butyrate and benzoate yields 2-methyl-4-benzoyl-6-acylphenols which are also obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzylation of 2-methyl-6-acylphenols.

In spite of the reported inhibition of the Fries reaction in presence of a negative group (Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56) several phenolic esters containing diverse negative groups have been studied during the last few years (Amin *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 617 and references cited therein). In continuation of such work, the Fries rearrangement of the esters of 2-methyl-4-benzoylphenol (I: R=H) has been described in the present communication.

2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl acetate (I: R=COMe) on heating with aluminium chloride afforded 2-methyl-4-benzoyl-6-acetylphenol (II: R=COMe) as only 6-position was vacant for the migrating group to occupy. That the -COMe group entered next to the -OH group was confirmed by preparing 2'-hydroxy-3'-methyl-5'-benzoyl-4-methoxychalkone and the corresponding 6-benzoyl-3-methyl-4'-methoxy-flavanoid derivatives, described earlier (Amin and Amin, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 126). The structure has been further confirmed by direct comparison with the product obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzylation of the known 2-methyl-6-acetylphenol.

Similarly, 2-methyl-4-benzoylphenyl propionate (I: R=COEt) and butyrate (I: R=COPr) on the Fries isomerisation furnished 2-methyl-4-benzoyl-6-propionyl- (II: R=COEt) and -6-butyryl- (II: R=COPr) phenols respectively, which were also prepared by the Friedel-Crafts benzylation of 2-methyl-6-propionyl-(III: R=COEt) and -6-butyryl (III: R=COPr)-phenols.

2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl benzoate (I: R=COPh) also furnished the expected 2-methyl-4:6-dibenzoylphenol (II: R=COPh). Since 2-methyl-6-benzoylphenol (III: R=COPh) could not be obtained under various conditions, the same product (II) was prepared by the Friedel-Crafts benzylation of 2-methyl-4-benzoylphenol (I: R=H) itself for direct comparison. Thus, in conformation with the previous observations for the Fries reaction in case of diverse negatively substituted phenolic esters, presence of the benzoyl group in the phenolic nucleus does not appear to inhibit or retard this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenol (I: R=H) was prepared by the Fries reaction of 2-methylphenyl benzoate (b.p. 307°) according to Rosenmund and Schnurr (*loc. cit.*), m.p. 169°, yield 70%. Cox (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 1028) records m.p. 173-74°.

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl Acetate (I : R=COMe) : Formation of 2-Methyl-4-benzoyl-6-acetylphenol (II : R=COMe)

The acetate (I : R=COMe) was prepared by $\text{Ac}_2\text{O-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ method in colorless needles (dilute acetic acid), m.p. 67° , yield 70%. (Found : C, 75.41 ; H, 5.32. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.60 ; H, 5.51%).

The acetate (I : R=COMe) (5 g., 1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.8 g., 3.3 M) were intimately mixed and heated at 160° for 2 hours (CaCl_2 -guard tube). At the end, the mixture was decomposed by ice and HCl (5 c.c.). The solid obtained was filtered, washed, and crystallised from ethanol in yellowish white, shining needles, m.p. 110° , yield 3 g. (Found : C 75.28 ; H, 5.44. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.60 ; H, 5.51%).

The product develops a deep violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and dissolves in NaOH and in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with a yellow colour. The other ketones described below also responded to the same tests.

The above reaction at 120° yielded lesser amount of the ketone (1.3 g.), and at 100° mainly unchanged ester was recovered. In nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) at 120° the ketone (1 g.) and uncrystallisable tarry product were obtained after removal of the nitrobenzene.

The dioxime of the above ketone, prepared as usual, was crystallised in yellowish small needles from ethanol, m.p. 207° (decomp.). (Found : N, 9.77. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.86%).

The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol as pale brown granules, m.p. 210° (decomp.). (Found : N, 22.57. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 22.81%).

The acetate, prepared by acetyl chloride-NaOH (5%) method, was crystallised from ethanol in almost colorless small needles, m. p. 67° . (Found : C, 72.64 ; H, 5.38. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.98 ; H, 5.41%).

Friedel-Crafts' Benzoylation of 2-Methyl-6-acetylphenol (III : R=COMe).—2-Methyl-6-acetylphenol (5 g., b.p. $107^\circ/10.5$ mm ; Anschutz, *Annalen*, 1925, 379, 342), aluminium chloride (10 g.) and benzoyl chloride (5 g.) were heated together at $150-60^\circ$ for 2 hours. The product obtained on decomposition of the reaction mixture by ice and HCl (5 c.c.) was filtered and crystallised from ethanol ; m.p. and the mixed m.p. with the Fries reaction product, 110° ; yield 2.5 g.

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl Propionate : Formation of 2-Methyl-4-benzoyl-6-propionylphenol (II : R=COEt)

The propionate (I : R=COEt) was prepared by propionic anhydride-pyridine method as slightly discoloured rhombic plates from ethanol, m.p. 66° . (Found : C, 75.88 ; H, 5.78. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.12 ; H, 5.97%).

The rearrangement of the propionate (I : R=COEt) (5 g., 1 M) by anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.3 g., 3.3 M) at 160° for 2 hours furnished a brownish solid after the usual treatment. It was crystallised from ethanol in light thin plates, m.p. 86° , yield 3.5 g. (Found : 76.02 ; H, 5.94. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.12 ; H, 5.97%).

The dioxime was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 188° (decomp.). (Found : N, 9.24. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.39%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised in yellowish thin needles, m.p. 210° (decomp.). (Found : N, 21.83. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3N_6$ requires N, 21.99%).

The *benzoate*, prepared by benzoyl chloride-sodium hydroxide (5%) method, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless thick needles, m.p. 84°. (Found : C, 77.08 ; H, 5.23. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 77.41 ; H, 5.38%).

Friedel-Crafts' Benzoylation of 2-Methyl-6-propionylphenol (III : R=COEt).—The *phenol* (III : R=COEt) was prepared by the Fries reaction of 2-methylphenyl propionate (b.p. 113°) at 160° for 2 hours. The oil obtained after the usual treatment distilled at 222-24°, yield 60%. (Found : C, 72.91 ; H, 7.09. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 73.17 ; H, 7.32%).

The above *ketone* was benzoylated as before at 160° for 2 hours in thin plates from ethanol; m.p. and the mixed m.p. with (II : R=COEt), 86°.

*Fries Rearrangement of 2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl Butyrate : Formation of
2-Methyl-4-benzoyl-6-butyrylphenol* (II : R=COPr)

The *butyrate* (I : R=COPr), prepared by butyryl chloride-pyridine method, distilled at 210°/10 mm, yield 40%. (Found : C, 76.37 ; H, 6.13. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 76.60 ; H, 6.38%).

The rearrangement was carried out as before. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in brownish shining plates, m.p. 75°, yield 2.5 g. (Found : C, 76.43 ; H, 6.09. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 76.60 ; H, 6.38%).

The *dioxime* was obtained as colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 171° (decomp.). (Found : N, 8.91. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.97%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish short needles, m.p. 196° (decomp.). (Found : N, 20.96. $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_6$ requires N, 21.21%).

The *acetate*, prepared by acetyl chloride-sodium hydroxide (5%) method, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless shining plates, m.p. 82°. (Found : C, 73.79 ; H, 6.03. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.08 ; H, 6.17%).

Friedel-Crafts' Benzoylation of 2-Methyl-6-butyrylphenol (III : R=COPr).—The benzoylation of 2-methyl-6-butyrylphenol (5 g., b.p. 143°/11mm; Coulthard *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) was carried out as before. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol in brownish shining plates ; m.p. and the mixed m.p. with the above Fries reaction product, 75°.

*Fries Rearrangement of 2-Methyl-4-benzoylphenyl Benzoate : Formation of
2-Methyl-4 : 6-dibenzoylphenol* (II : R=COPh)

The *benzoate* (I : R=COPh) was prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method in colorless shining needles from ethanol, m.p. 102°. (Found : C, 79.48 ; H, 4.93. $C_{21}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 79.75 ; H, 5.06%).

The mixture of the benzoate (I : R=COPh) (5 g., 1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (7 g., 3.3 M) was heated at 160° for 2 hours as before. After the usual treatment, the solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol in yellowish, thin, rhombic plates, m.p. 95°, yield 2.2 g. (Found : C, 79.61 ; H, 4.87. $C_{21}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 79.75 ; H, 5.06%).

The *dioxime* was obtained in thin needles from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 186° (decomp.). (Found : N, 7.86. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.04%).

The *semicarbazone* was obtained as colorless shining needles from ethanol, m.p. 195° (decomp.). (Found : N, 19.42. $C_{23}H_{22}O_3N_6$ requires N, 19.54%).

The *acetate* was prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method as colorless, shining, small granules from ethanol, m.p. 142°. (Found : C, 76.70 ; H, 4.92. $C_{23}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 77.09 ; H, 5.03%).

Friedel-Crafts' benzylation of 2-methyl-4-benzoylphenol (5 g.) (I : R=COPh) by benzoyl chloride (6 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) gave the product on the usual treatment. It was crystallised from ethanol as yellowish, thin, rhombic plates ; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above ketone, 95° ; yield 3 g.

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